

PRINCIPALS' LEADERSHIP STYLES AND STUDENTS' DISCIPLINE IN PUPBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN EKITI STATE, NIGERIA

FAREMI, MARGARET FUNKE¹, OLASEINDE, FELICIA OLUFEMI²,
BOLARINWA, DAPO ALONGE^{3*}, BELO, FAWZIYAH ABIMBOLA⁴ and
OGUNLADE, ABIGAIL TOYIN⁵

¹Faculty of Education, Department of Educational Management, Osun State University, Osogbo, Nigeria.

²Faculty of Education, Department of Arts and Language Education, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

^{3,5}Faculty of Education, Department of Educational Management, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

⁴Faculty of Education, Department of Educational Foundations and Management, College of Education, Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology, Ikere-Ekiti, Nigeria.

Email: ¹margaret.faremi@uniosun.edu.ng, ²Felicia.olaseinde@eksu.edu.ng,

³dapo.bolarinwa@eksu.edu.ng (*Corresponding Author), ⁴belo.fawziyah@bouesti.edu.ng,

⁵abigail.ogunlade@eksu.edu.ng

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the level of discipline; and the relationship between principals' leadership styles and students' discipline. The population of the study consisted of 7,538 teachers and all the students in 206 public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted of 105 respondents. Multistage sampling procedure was used for the study. The first stage involved the use of simple random sampling technique to select seven Local Government Areas out of 16. The second stage involved the use of simple random sampling technique to select 15 schools from each of the Local Government Areas. The third stage involved the use of proportionate sampling technique to select 49 teachers and 56 students because; the schools did not have the same number of teachers and students. The instruments used were Principal' Leadership Style Questionnaire and Students' Discipline Questionnaire and the reliability (r) coefficients were 0.78 and 0.84 respectively. A 4-point rating scale was employed for the instruments. The null hypotheses formulated for the study was tested at 0.05 level of significant. The study revealed that the level of students' discipline in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria was high; there was significant relationship between principals' autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire leadership styles and students' discipline.

Keywords: Leadership, Leadership Styles, Discipline, Students' Discipline, Principals' Leadership Styles.

INTRODUCTION

The discipline of students in secondary schools is an important factor in ensuring a productive learning environment. It is not merely the enforcement of rules, but the process of guiding students towards self-regulation, responsibility, and respect for the rights of others. According to Kibet, Kindiki, Sang and Kitilit (2012), discipline is a role of administration and therefore, the school principals should offer good management skills in order to have students with acceptable behaviours. Despite various efforts to maintain discipline in schools, many schools continue to experience challenges such as truancy, bullying, disrespect for authority, and defiance of school rules. According to Adegbesan (2011) cited in Amaefule and Amaechi (2020) who opined that in Nigeria, secondary school students perpetrate act of indiscipline which is contrary to the school rules and regulations. They leave the school premises without

permission. Therefore, these behaviours can disrupt the learning environment and negatively affect both student' academic performance and overall school climate. According to Dunham (2015), effective discipline helps in the achievement of goals, expectation and responsibility in students.

It has been observed that some students do not follow the school rules and regulations; arrive at school on time every day; attend classes; wear the appropriate school uniform; and respect his or her mates and teachers. In support of the above assertions, Ani (2021) reported that a Junior Secondary School one student, Gift Agenoisa of Mary Immaculate Secondary School, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria was in the school premises during the school hours with indecent hairstyle and because she was corrected, the father of the student, a police officer sued the school Principal, the Commissioner of Education, the Ekiti State Teaching Service Commission, and the Ekiti State Government.

Furthermore, it appears, some students do not submit assignments on time; and participate in school activities without causing trouble. The problem is further compounded by the developmental needs of secondary school students, who are at a critical stage of adolescence, which appears to make them more prone to testing boundaries and authority. According to Okoth and Kathuri (2018), when students feel marginalised and their opinions are ignored, their engagement in school decreases, leading to higher rates of absenteeism and increased disciplinary infractions. This lack of autonomy can foster disengagement and resentment, particularly among adolescents who are naturally inclined towards developing independence. Ayeleso (2024) reported that a former Commissioner for Education, Science, and Technology in Ekiti State, Nigeria has expressed concern over the declining level of moral discipline in primary and secondary schools across the county and that he advocated for a return to an era of corrective discipline for students to foster a better and more upright society in the future.

Principals play a crucial role in establishing a disciplinary framework that is aligned with the values of the school. According to Arum and Beattie (2019), the success of school discipline policies largely depends on the leadership style adopted by the principal. In support, Amaefule and Amaechi (2020) opined that it may be difficult to adequately install discipline in schools without good principals' leadership styles. More so, Ali, Dada, Isiaka and Salmon (2014) asserted that a school that has good discipline is the one that whose students adhere to the rules and regulations of the school. In such a school, few or not indiscipline cases are reported and students are motivated to do what is right even with little or no teacher supervision.

A principal's ability to balance firmness with empathy often determines the effectiveness of disciplinary measure. The influence of principal leadership on student discipline extends beyond policy enforcement; it encompasses proactive measures such as mentoring programmes, conflict resolution strategies, and restorative justice approaches. By adopting these approaches, principals can mitigate disruptive behaviour and promote a culture of accountability and mutual responsibility within the school community. According to Umezina and Elendu (2012) cited in Amaefule and Amaechi (2020), discipline is a role of administration and therefore, the school principals should offer good management skills in order to have students with accepted behaviour. In support, Ouma, Simatwa and Serem (2013)

cited in Amaefule and Amaechi (2020) opined that based on the assertions of Umezinwa and Elendu (2012), schools are meant to teach morals that are needed within the school and outside the school which are necessary as students grow up to be responsible members of the society. More so, Kiprop (2012) opined that discipline in schools is function of the administration, and therefore, the principal as a leader must have a clear discipline policy of what is required for the successful management of school discipline.

Laissez-faire or free-rein leadership style is characterised by minimal direct supervision and a hands-off approach to decision-making. In educational setting, this leadership style involves principals providing teachers and students with significant autonomy, often refraining from imposing stringent guidelines or rules. It can encourage innovation and creativity by giving teachers and students the freedom to explore different approaches to learning and problem-solving. For schools where students' behaviour can be particularly volatile, a more balanced leadership approach is often required to ensure that the autonomy provided does not lead to a breakdown in order. This style which emphasises motivation, inspiration, and a shared vision, has been linked with positive school environments where students are less likely to engage in deviant behaviours like stealing, truancy, and improper dressing.

Aside the above solutions to indiscipline, autocratic leadership style often define by its authoritarian nature, entails a principal making all critical decisions with little or no input from the teachers and students. According to Bush and Glover (2014), this leadership style is sometimes perceived as necessary in schools facing significant discipline problems as the principal can swiftly implement rules and consequences without the need for extensive consultation. However, the emphases on strict control can lead to an atmosphere of fear and resentment which might encourage students to rebel rather than conform to the desired behavioural norm. Ibrahim and Orodho (2014) asserted that such rigid control stifles students' ability to self-discipline and critical thinking skills.

The relationship between principal autocratic leadership style and student discipline must also be understood in the context of teacher-student interactions. In schools headed by principals with autocratic style of leadership, teachers may adopt similarly autocratic approach in their classrooms which can further alienate students. According to Omolade (2021), students in such an environment may experience higher levels of stress and anxiety contributing to behavioural issues and defiance against authority members.

Democratic leadership style which emphasises participatory decision-making, collaboration, and shared responsibility has gained recognition as an effective leadership style in promoting discipline in schools. It enables students to have a voice in the policies and rules that govern their behaviour which enhances their willingness to comply with the school regulations. According to Ukpong (2017), this leadership approach allows for a balanced interaction between school leaders, teachers, students, and other stakeholders fostering a sense of ownership and mutual respect that positively influence students' behaviour. However, democratic leadership style enhances teacher involvement in maintaining discipline. Teachers are encouraged to participate in decision-making process regarding discipline policies and classroom strategies. This participatory approach not only strengthens the bond between the

principals and teachers but ensures consistency in disciplinary enforcement across the school. Leithwood (2019) opined that when teachers are empowered and their professional judgement is respected, it results in a more cohesive effort to maintain discipline and creates a positive school culture where students are motivated to adhere to rules.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Discipline

Discipline comes from a Latin word that means come learn a master and so, discipline can be defined as the process of learning so as to train the mind and character in order to produce self-control. Ali, Dada, Isiaka and Salmon (2014) asserted that discipline is the practice of care and respect for others and self. It is about safeguarding the rights of people who are exposed to uncooperative, aggressive or blocking responses by others. According to Adesina (1980) cited in Bolarinwa (2016), discipline is to teach students to respect the school authorities, to observe the school rules and regulations, and to maintain an established standard of behaviour. In support of the above, Abubakar (2000) cited in Bolarinwa (2016) went further to define discipline as the ability and willingness to do what one ought to do without external control or prompting.

To some people, discipline connotes something negative as obeying orders blindly, kneeling down, doing manual work, fetching firewood and water for teachers and parents, caning and other forms of punishment. Ngonyami (2013) said, discipline involves the preparation of an individual to be a complete and efficient member of a community; and a disciplined member of a community is one who knows his or her right and obligations to their community.

According to Sushila (2004) cited in Kibet, Kindiki, Sang and Kitilit (2012), discipline is the process of training or controlling often using a system of punishment aimed at causing the recipients to obey rules. Nyabisi (2008) cited in Kibet, Kindiki, Sang and Kitilit (2012) opined that discipline should not be a way to control students but a process of education to improve and perfect behaviour aimed at obedience to rules based on self-control and self-discipline. According to Godson-Wejimogu and Obialo (2020), discipline is not set of rules, not regulations, not punishments; it is not compliance nor obedience nor enforcement. The modern concept of discipline is choice and decision to learn and apply intentional standards to achieve meaningful objectives.

Leadership Styles

Leadership styles are the process and method of getting people to do what the leader wants. That is, the right of a manager to assign duties to subordinates. In order to get the best results from the subordinates, managers must be able to raise subordinates' morale by implication, a spirit of involvement and cooperation and willingness to work. According to Fadia (2016), leadership styles are the pattern of behaviours that a leader exhibits in influencing his or her subordinates. Northouse (2021) asserted that leaders usually exhibit a style of leadership as they motivate and inspire their followers. He said, leadership therefore, refers to the manner in which a leader chooses to lead and interact with their followers. Darny (2016) opined that

leadership style reflects the leader's behaviours, attitudes, and actions in influencing and directing others. According to Newstrom and Davis (2018), leadership is the method and approach to providing direction, implementing plans, and motivating people. As seen by the employees, it includes the total pattern of explicit and implicit actions performed by their leaders.

According to Dubrin (2015), there are several leadership styles and these different leadership styles can impact the dynamics, productivity, and culture within an organisation or group in several different ways. Wehrich (2017) mentioned the three major leadership styles as autocratic, laissez-faire, and democratic. These are leadership styles which concerns the contingency theory assumptions. In modern leadership theories, five leadership styles have been presented to include: charismatic, transactional, democratic, visionary, and cultured-based leadership styles.

A study conducted by Amaefule and Amaechi (2020) on principals' leadership styles and students' discipline in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria revealed that the extent to which principals' autocratic and democratic leadership styles influenced students' discipline in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria were moderate. Njami and Bula (2018) conducted a study on assessment of principals' leadership styles on students' discipline in public secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya revealed that there was a significant relationship between principals' democratic and autocratic styles of leadership and students' discipline.

A study conducted by Kilemi (2018) on the influence of principals' leadership styles on students' discipline in public secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya revealed that democratic leadership was established to be the most favourable leadership approach in schools. Mudanyi, Ajowi and Mwebi (2022) conducted a study on the effect of principals' leadership styles on school discipline in public secondary schools in Vihiga Sub-County, Kenya revealed that there was low level of discipline in most of the secondary schools in Vihiga Sub-County.

A study conducted by Oboshi and Okoli (2021) on the relationship between principals' leadership styles and disciplinary problems in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria revealed that democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles were the best and suitable styles used by principals for curbing indiscipline among students; and that autocratic leadership style was unpopular among principals in urban secondary schools. Kibet, Kindiki, Sang and Kitilit (2012) conducted a study on principal leadership and its impact on students' discipline in Kenyan secondary schools: A case of Koibatek District found out a positive relationship between leadership styles and students' discipline. Atitwa (2025) conducted a study on laissez-faire leadership and students' discipline in public secondary schools in Teso North Sub-County, Kenya revealed that no significant correlation was determined.

Contingency Theory

This theory as propounded by Fiedler (1967) was also known as Fiedler contingency theory. Situation and contingency theories are often considered as revolutionary approaches to the

study of leadership. Therefore, while the situational theory merely indicates the importance of organisational situation on leadership behaviour, the contingency theory prescribes which leadership behaviour will yield the best results in a specific situation. The theory advocated that there was no one best way of organising things. It allows for flexibility in solving complex problems by the managers. Thus, whatever success might be achieved by managers is product of the situation of the organisation. For example, in an organisation where resources are grossly inadequate, there is low staff morale, and the staff are not motivate, democratic style of leadership might be the best while where resources are adequate, the staff morale is high, and the staff are adequately motivated, autocratic style of leadership might be the best.

According to Koontz et al (1980) cited in Ekundayo (2023), Fiedler's theory implies that leadership is to exercise influence depending upon the group task situation and the degree to which the leader's style, personality, and approach fit the group. More so, Fiedler (1980) cited in Ekundayo (2023) opined that people become leaders not only because of the attributes of their personality but also because of various situational factors and the interaction between the leaders and the situation. To relate the above theory with this study, the principals need to consider the situation of the school (indiscipline among the students). Since the contingency theory implies that leadership is to exercise influence depending upon the group task situation and the degree to which the leader's style, personality, and approach fit the group, then, democratic style of leadership will be appropriate to tackle indiscipline in schools.

Research Questions

This research question was raised for the study:

1. What is the level of students' discipline in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated for the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' autocratic leadership style and students' discipline.
2. There is no significant relationship between principals' laissez-faire leadership style and students' discipline
3. There is no significant relationship between principals' democratic leadership style and students' discipline.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research design of the survey and correlational was adopted for the study. This because, it focuses on the observation and performance of the existing situation, describes and interprets what is concerned with issues, conditions, practice or relationship that exist; views, belief and attitude that are held, processes that are going on and trends that are developing. As at the time of this study, the population of the study consisted 7,538 teachers and all the students

in 206 public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample of the study consisted of 105 respondents. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used for the study. In the first stage, simple random sampling technique was used to select seven Local Government Areas out of the 16 Local Government Areas. The second stage involved the use of simple random sampling technique to select 15 schools from each of the seven Local Government Areas. The third stage involved the use of proportionate sampling technique to select 49 teachers and 56 students because; the schools did not have equal number of teachers and students.

The instrument tagged ‘‘Principals’ Leadership Styles Questionnaire’’ (PLSQ) and ‘‘Students’ Discipline Questionnaire’’ (SDQ) were designed and adopted to collect data for this study. A 4-point rating scale was employed for the instruments. The instruments were shown to specialists in the area of Tests and Measurement and Educational Management who checked and read the contents for adequate coverage of the topic and clarity of the items for face and content validity. The reliability co-efficient (r) calculated were 0.78 and 0.84 for PLSQ and SDQ respectively through test-re-test methods, which were high enough to ensure the reliability of the instruments. The two sets of the instrument were administered personally by the researchers. The hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson’s product moment correlation statistics.

RESULTS

Table 1: Level of students’ discipline

Items	SA		A		D		SD		Mean
	f	%	F	%	f	%	%	f	
I follow all school rules and regulations	66	66.0	28	28.0	5	5.0	1	1.0	3.45
I arrive at school on time every day	70	70.0	27	27.0	2	2.0	1	1.0	3.65
I arrive at classes on time ever day	66	66.0	31	31.0	2	2.0	1	1.0	3.58
I always wear the appropriate school uniform	57	57.0	35	35.0	4	4.0	4	4.0	3.50
I treat my teachers with respect	65	65.0	29	29.0	4	4.0	2	2.0	3.58
I treat my classmates with respect	66	66.0	21	21.0	7	7.0	6	6.0	3.47
I avoid engaging in fights with other students	71	71.0	22	22.0	5	5.0	2	2.0	3.62
I submit my assignments on time	69	69.0	26	26.0	3	3.0	2	2.0	3.63
I avoid bringing prohibited items (phones, weapons) to school	60	60.0	12	12.0	17	17.0	11	11.0	3.21
I stay attentive disruptive behaviour in class	61	61.0	32	32.0	5	5.0	2	2.0	3.52
I stay avoid disruptive behaviour in class	64	64.0	31	31.0	4	4.0	1	1.0	3.58
I take responsibility for my actions when I break a school rule	60	60.0	32	32.0	6	6.0	2	2.0	3.50
I participate in school activities without causing trouble	61	61.0	32	32.0	5	5.0	2	2.0	3.52
									3.52

Mean cut-off: 2.50

Table 1 shows the item analysis of level of discipline in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Using a criterion mean of 2.50 for the rating scale, all the items had mean score above the cut-off point. This means, there is high level of discipline.

Table 2: Relationship between principals’ autocratic leadership style and students’ discipline

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value
Principals’ autocratic leadership style	105	3.71	0.74	0.412*	0.001
Students’ discipline	105	3.85	0.33		

*p<0.005

Table 2 shows the relationship between principals’ autocratic leadership style and students’ discipline. The result shows that the value of r-calculated (0.412) is greater than p-value (0.001). Therefore, the null hypothesis earlier formulated is rejected. This then means that there is significant relationship between principals’ autocratic leadership style and students’ discipline.

Table 3: Relationship between principals’ democratic leadership style and students’ discipline

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value
Principals’ democratic leadership style	105	2.77	0.28	0.317*	0.001
Students’ discipline	105	3.85	0.33		

*p<0.05

Table 3 shows the relationship between principals’ democratic leadership style and students’ discipline. The result shows that the value of r-calculated (0.317) is greater than p-value (0.001). Therefore, the null hypothesis earlier formulated is rejected. This then means that there is significant relationship between principals’ democratic leadership style and students’ discipline.

Table 4: Relationship between principals’ laissez-faire leadership style and students’ discipline

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value
Principals’ laissez-faire leadership style	105	3.14	0.41	0.485*	0.001
Students’ discipline	105	3.85	0.33		

*p<0.05

Table 4 shows the relationship between principals’ laissez-faire leadership style and students’ discipline. The result shows that the value of r-calculated (0.485) is greater than p-value (0.001). Therefore, the null hypothesis earlier formulated is rejected. This then means that there is significant relationship between principals’ laissez-faire leadership style and students’ discipline.

DISCUSSION

The study revealed that the level of students’ discipline in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria was high. This might be because of the appropriate leadership employed by the principals. This finding is supported by Arum and Beattie (2019) who opined that the success of school discipline policies largely depends on the leadership style employed by the principals;

Ibrahim and Orodho (2014) who opined that such rigid control (autocratic leadership) stifles students' ability to develop self-discipline and critical thinking skills; Ukpong (2017) who said that this leadership approach (democratic leadership style) allows for a balanced interaction between school leaders, teachers, students, and other stakeholders, fostering a sense of ownership and mutual respect that positively influences students' behaviour; and Leithwood (2019) who opined that when teachers are empowered and their professional judgement is respected, it results in a more cohesive effort to maintain discipline and creates a positive school culture where students are motivated to adhere to rules.

The study revealed that there was a significant relationship between principals' autocratic leadership style and students' discipline. This implies that principals' autocratic leadership style enhanced students' discipline. This could be because of the principals' ability to use the style effectively. This finding is in support of Fadia (2016) who said that leadership styles are the pattern of behaviours that a leader exhibits in influencing his or her subordinates; Northouse (2021) who asserted that leaders usually exhibit a style of leadership as they motivate and inspire their followers. He said, leadership therefore, refers to the manner in which a leader chooses to lead and interact with their followers; Darny (2016) who opined that leadership style reflects the leader's behaviours, attitudes, and actions in influencing and directing others; Newstrom and Davis (2018) who said that leadership is the method and approach to providing direction, implementing plans, and motivating people. As seen by the employees, it includes the total pattern of explicit and implicit actions performed by their leaders; Amaefule and Amaechi (2020) who revealed that the extent to which principals' autocratic and democratic leadership styles influenced students' discipline in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria were moderate; Njami and Bula (2018) who revealed that there was a significant relationship between principals' democratic and autocratic styles of leadership and students' discipline; and Kibet, Kindiki, Sang and Kitilit (2012) who found out a positive relationship between leadership styles and students' discipline.

The study revealed that there was a significant relationship between principals' democratic leadership style and students' discipline. This implies that principals' democratic style enhanced discipline. This might be because the principals were able to use this style effectively. Amaefule and Amaechi (2020) who revealed that the extent to which principals' autocratic and democratic leadership styles influenced students' discipline in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria were moderate; Njami and Bula (2018) who revealed that there was a significant relationship between principals' democratic and autocratic styles of leadership and students' discipline; Kilemi (2018) who revealed that democratic leadership was established to be the most favourable leadership approach in schools; Oboshi and Okoli (2021) who revealed that democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles were the best and suitable styles used by principals for curbing indiscipline among students; and Kibet, Kindiki, Sang and Kitilit (2012) who found out a positive relationship between leadership styles and students' discipline.

The study revealed that there was a significant relationship between principals' laissez-faire leadership style and students' discipline. This means, principals' laissez-faire leadership style enhanced students' discipline. This might be because of the principals' ability to use the style

effectively. This finding corroborate that of Fadia (2016) who said that leadership styles are the pattern of behaviours that a leader exhibits in influencing his or her subordinates; Northouse (2021) who asserted that leaders usually exhibit a style of leadership as they motivate and inspire their followers. He said, leadership therefore, refers to the manner in which a leader chooses to lead and interact with their followers; Darny (2016) who opined that leadership style reflects the leader's behaviours, attitudes, and actions in influencing and directing others; Newstrom and Davis (2018) who said that leadership is the method and approach to providing direction, implementing plans, and motivating people. As seen by the employees, it includes the total pattern of explicit and implicit actions performed by their leaders; Oboshi and Okoli (2021) who revealed that democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles were the best and suitable styles used by principals for curbing indiscipline among students; and Kibet, Kindiki, Sang and Kitilit (2012) who found out a positive relationship between leadership styles and students' discipline.

CONCLUSION

This paper reviewed various literatures that are relevant to principals' leadership styles and students' discipline. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the level of students' discipline was high; and principals' autocratic, democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles enhanced students' discipline.

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